

MATHEMATICAL MODELLING OF RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING OF COMPOSITES FOR AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The filling stage of the Resin Transfer Model (RTM) is described through the development of a two dimensional model based on the solution of Darcy's equation for flow in porous media. Model results are expressed in terms of pressure-flow rate relationships and total filling time as function of the operating pressure, for processes conducted at constant flow rate or constant pressure respectively. Moreover, model results are compared with results obtained with commercial injection molding packages properly modified to account for the effect of the porous media on the mold thickness and resin viscosity. Finally, several methods for the experimental determination of fiber bed permeabilities are discussed.

Key Words: Composites, Resin Transfer Molding, Mathematical model

1. INTRODUCTION

Low and medium performance composites produced by Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) are being currently considered as alternatives for automotive applications. The main advantage offered by this technology is the flexibility to produce low weight complex geometry parts more simply and much faster than in other composite technologies. However, the necessity to guarantee a perfect wettability of a higher volume of fibers with a high viscosity during mold filling represents a challenging problem. The determination of the required processing conditions has been approached in this work by developing a mathematical model of the flow of a thermosetting polymer filling a heated mold with a preplaced fiber bed with anisotropic permeability.

The first attempts to apply the theory of flow in porous media to the processing of polymeric composite materials were performed to analyze the consolidation of epoxy matrix laminates in the vacuum bag autoclave process (1-4). The resin flow through the fibers was described in all those cases by applying Darcy's Law. More recently, in parallel with the development of RTM processes, the impregnation of fiber preforms during mold filling has been addressed using the same fluidynamic concepts (5-7). If the mold thickness is much smaller than its width or length, impregnation of fiber homogeneous preforms can be also simulated through the Hele-Shaw model for injection molding (14). As pointed out by Lee et al. (15), mold thickness and resin viscosity must be properly modified to account for the effect of porous medium. However, the reported models have not been utilized so far to develop useful technological informations on the effect of different processing conditions and material properties on the overall process performance. In this work a

preliminar analysis of the capabilities of the mathematical modelling of the RTM process based on Darcy's law to be used for practical purposes is presented. Moreover, model results are compared with results obtained with a commercial injection molding package (FABEST).

2. RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING MODEL

The complex fluidynamic characteristics of the mold filling in the presence of a fibrous preform in RTM can be described either through a microscopic or macroscopic approach. The microscopic approach requires to account for all the boundary conditions provided by the presence of the fiber in the flow field. Then, the Navier-Stokes can be applied to the flow around the fibers and a necessary simplification about uniform fiber distribution and orientation must be included. On the other hand, a more practical model can be obtained through the application of a macroscopic approach considering the fibrous bed as a continuous porous media characterized by two average constants depending on the fiber content and geometry: porosity and permeability. In this case the fluid flow during mold filling is assumed to be described by an average plug-flow in the porous media that does not consider the interaction fluid-wall at the fiber boundaries. With these main assumptions, verified in the case that the porous dimension is much smaller than the mold thickness, the relationship between the fluid velocity (\underline{v}) and the pressure gradient (∇P) can be described empirically by the Darcy's Law (8-10):

$$\underline{v} = -(1/\mu) \underline{k} \nabla P \quad (1)$$

where μ is the fluid viscosity and \underline{k} is the permeability tensor. Very often and depending on the specific requirements of the composite design the fiber bed is anisotropic and different permeabilities, represented by the diagonal components of \underline{k} , characterize the fluid flow in different directions. It has been reported that Darcy's law can be applied when the following conditions are completed: laminar flow, Newtonian and homogeneous flow, steady state flow, inertial forces negligible with respect to viscous flow. These conditions can be expressed using the Reynolds number ($Re = \rho v d/\mu$) defined in terms of the characteristic porous dimension, d . Bear (9) reported the validity of the Darcy's law for Re ranging in the interval between 1 and 10 that can be easily verified by the reactive pre-polymers used in the filling stage of RTM.

Figure 1: Geometric scheme of the RTM mold adopted for the mathematical model

The two dimensional model presented in this work corresponds to the filling of a rectangular cavity, previously filled with an eventually anisotropic fiber bed, with a Newtonian incompressible fluid. The mold thickness is assumed to be much smaller than the other two dimensions. The mold geometry and coordinates used to develop the model are shown in Fig. 1. Applying the continuity equation ($\nabla \cdot \underline{v} = 0$) to Eqn. 1 in two dimensions the following expression gives the relationship between the system permeability and the pressure field:

$$k_x (\partial^2 P / \partial x^2) + k_y (\partial^2 P / \partial y^2) = 0 \quad (2)$$

For an isotropic and constant permeability tensor Eq. 2 reduces to Laplace equation. Eq. 2 must be integrated considering the values of the pressure and of its derivatives at the flow field boundaries. Pressure at the flow front (P_f) is considered constant and equal to the pressure previously imposed in the mold that is normally the atmospheric pressure or lower if vacuum is applied:

$$P = P_f \quad \text{at} \quad F[x_f(t), y_f(t)] = 0 \quad (3)$$

where $F[x_f(t), y_f(t)] = 0$ describes the form of the front at a generic time t . For the pressure at the gate two different situations can be ipotized. The process can be performed imposing at the gate (assumed of circular form with radius R_g) a pressure ($P_0(t)$):

$$P = P_0 \quad \text{for} \quad x^2 + y^2 = R_g^2 \quad (4)$$

or imposing the flow rate ($Q(t)$). Following Darcy's Law this last case is equivalent to impose the pressure gradient at the gate:

$$Q(t)/A_g = - (1/\mu) \underline{k} (\nabla P)_0 \underline{n}_0 \quad (5)$$

where \underline{n}_0 is the normal versor at the gate boundaries and A_g represents the gate area. At the mold walls, the no flow condition gives:

$$\begin{aligned} x = \pm a & \quad \partial P / \partial x = 0 & (6) \\ y = \pm b & \quad \partial P / \partial y = 0 & (7) \end{aligned}$$

The system of Eqns. 2 to 7 is a classical moving boundary problem where the integration field is variable during the filling time and represents one of the unknowns to be solved. Its solution gives the pressure distribution and the flow front position as a function of time. Successive application of Eqn. 1 gives the velocity field. The complexity of the system requires, in most cases, the application of numerical techniques. In this research finite differences in two dimensions were used. The code developed uses Gauss-Seidel method to solve the algebraic system obtained after discretization. The relative position of the front with respect to the fixed mesh after each time step is computed using the velocity field at the previous time step.

The Hele-Shaw model has been developed starting from lubrication theory (14) and holds for the same assumptions, i.e. creeping flow of a newtonian incompressible fluid through slowly varying, relatively narrow gaps. Averaged effective velocities u_{iS} and u_{yS} defined as

$$u_{iS} = \frac{1}{h_s} \int_0^{h_s} u_i dz \quad i=x,y \quad (8)$$

where h_s is the mold thickness, are related to pressure gradient through the following relationship

$$\underline{u}_S = (h_s^2 / 12 \mu_S) \nabla P \quad (9)$$

while continuity equation gives

$$\nabla^2 P = 0 \quad (10)$$

The velocity and pressure fields described by Eq. (9) and (10) and those described by Eq. (1) and (2) for homogeneous medium ($k_x=k_y$) are formally identical. Then, if effective velocities are used in Eq.(1) and the same boundary conditions are used in the two cases, the two sets of equations can be made equivalent when the following conditions are met:

$$h_s^2 / 12 \mu_S = k / \mu \epsilon \quad (11)$$

$$h_s = h \epsilon \quad (12)$$

The last equation states the geometrical similarity between a mold of thickness h filled with fibrous preform and a fictitious mold of thickness h_s without fibrous preform.

The occurrence of this mathematical similarity allows to use computer codes for injection molding to simulate the isothermal filling of a homogeneous preform. The fictitious resin viscosity μ_s and mold thickness h_s given by Eqs. (11) and (12) must be used in order to obtain the exact solution for pressure and velocity fields in RTM process.

3. MODEL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The model developed was applied to simulate the filling stage of a square mold during RTM process using an anisotropic preform. While model results are shown in Figures 2-5 in dimensionless form, the parameters and material properties used in the simulation are shown in Table 1. Working at constant imposed pressure the flow rate will decrease continuously during filling. This behavior is reported in Fig. 2 for three different processing pressures. This information can be used to regulate the applied pressure in order to avoid very high flow rates during the first part of the process or very low flow rates, with consequent very high filling times, in the last part. However, the most useful information that can be obtained from the simulation is shown in Fig. 3 where the time needed to fill the mold is represented as a function of the constant pressure applied during the process.

Figure 2: Flow rate at the gate as a function of time during the filling of an anisotropic preform filled at three different constant pressures.

Figure 3: Filling time as a function of the operating pressure during the filling of an anisotropic preform at different constant pressures.

It should be noted that each point in Fig. 3 corresponds to one complete run of the model. The hyperbolic form of the fitting curve confirms the inverse proportionality between the filling time and the applied pressure already suggested by the simplest form of Darcy's law. Also the case of mold filling at constant flow rate has been simulated. Working at constant flow rate the pressure at the gate must be continuously increased as shown in the results reported in Fig. 4 at different operating flow rates. The change in the curve pattern corresponds to the point where the flow front meets the mold wall. The information given in Fig. 4 is directly applied in practice to determine the pressure requirements or the maximum flow rate achieved for a given equipment. Finally, also in this case the final filling time has been computed as a function of the final applied pressure and represented in Fig.5. Obviously in this case longer times are obtained with respect to Fig. 3 results obtained at constant pressure operating during the full cycle.

Figure 4: Operating pressure as a function of time during the filling of an anisotropic preform filled at three different flow rates.

Figure 5: Filling time as a function of the final operating pressure during the filling of an anisotropic preform filled at different constant flow rates.

Table 1: Input data for RTM process simulation

Fiber bed permeabilities	$k_x = 2.0 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ m}^2;$	$k_y = 2.0 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$
Resin viscosity	$\mu = 1.0 \cdot 10^{-1} \text{ Pa s}$	
Porosity	$\epsilon = 50\%$	
Mold half length in x direction	$a = 0.40 \text{ m}$	
Mold half length in y direction	$b = 0.40 \text{ m}$	

A parametric analysis can be performed applying the model developed. In Fig. 6 the influence of the material properties on the total filling time is shown for different constant operating pressures. In particular the effect of the parameter $k/(\mu\epsilon)$ has been simulated for the filling of a square mold with an isotropic preform. The parallel behavior observed in Figure 6 suggests that simple correlations could be obtained to develop a master curve of the filling process.

Figure 6: Filling time as a function of the ratio $k/\mu\epsilon$ obtained at different constant operating pressures.

A commercial software package (FABEST), using a control-volume approach to solve Hele-Shaw model, has been utilized to simulate the filling stage of the homogeneous preform reported in fig. 7, where the adopted discretization grid for numerical calculation is also drawn. The final product is part of a car platform made completely in a structural polymeric matrix composite. The preform has a permeability of $8.0 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$ and a porosity of 0.9, while the viscosity of the injected resin (Modar 8365) was 250 mPa s at 20°C.

Figure 7: Discretization grid for the filling simulation of a car platform.

The input parameters were modified following Eqs. (11) and (12) to account for the effects of the porous medium. A filling time of 3.55 sec and a final flow rate of $5.4 \cdot 10^3 \text{ cc/min}$ were calculated for the injection process at a constant pressure of 10 bars. The same simulation has been performed using the finite differences code that solves §Darcy's law for an equivalent geometry. The geometrical equivalence was realized by considering a rectangular flat mold with the same width, thickness and total volume of the previous case. The filling time and final flow rate, calculated in the same conditions, were 3.63 sec and $5.2 \cdot 10^3 \text{ cc/min}$. In spite of the two different adopted geometries both codes gave practically the same result in terms of flow rates and filling times, as a consequence of the little influence that the mold curvature and gravitational effects have on the filling stage.

4. PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENT

In principle the fiber permeability can be measured following Darcy's Law (Eq. 6) from the relationship between the flow rate and the applied pressure in an instrumented mold. Some conditions must be imposed in order to obtain reliable data (8-10): steady state, isothermal and one-dimensional flow, rigid mold, uniform fiber distribution and constant Newtonian viscosity fluid. Traditional instruments available for the determination of the permeability normally operate at constant low pressure (10^5 Pa) and with low viscosity liquids. For example, when this instruments are used for RTM systems (see Table 1) very long times (1 day) are needed to complete a measurement. New instruments have been developed recently operating in the desired range (12,13).

4.1.a Constant pressure method a).

The use of dies provided with a transparent cover allows the visualization of the flow during filling. Normally a thick PMMA plate is used for the cover. In this experiment the position of the front (x_f) can be measured during filling in non-steady state conditions working with a constant pressure at the gate, and from the integration of Darcy's Law the expression to compute the permeability can be obtained:

$$k = x_f [\epsilon (\mu/2) / (P_O - P_f) t]^{1/2} \quad (13)$$

4.1.b Constant pressure method b).

To avoid front detection during constant pressure experiments, dies can be equipped with several pressure transducers to have pressure measurements between the front position and the injection gate. For one-dimensional flow, an instantaneous linear pressure distribution is realized in the mold, that is

$$(P_O - P(x,t)) / (P_O - P_f) = x/x_f(t) \quad (14)$$

where $P(x,t)$ is the pressure at the location x in the mold. Then, substituting Eq. (13), one obtains

$$\phi(t) = \frac{P_O - P(x,t)}{x \sqrt{P_O - P_f}} = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon \mu}{2k}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} \quad (15)$$

Experimental values of $\phi(t)$ can be calculated through the assigned or measured values of P_O , x , $P(x,t)$.

Figure 8: Permeability evaluation in constant pressure experiments.

The plot of ϕ as a function of $1/\sqrt{t}$ gives a straight line which slope ($\mu\epsilon/2k$) allows the computation of the reinforcement permeability. Several data for different values of the injection pressure can be collected together to give a better estimation of the permeability. This method has been applied to evaluate the permeability of a carbon fiber preform (BROCHIER SA Injetex E3285, 5H Satin 6K) with a void porosity $\epsilon=0.38$. The results are shown in Fig. 8 and the permeability has been evaluated to be $3.5 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$.

4.2 Constant flow rate method.

If the total pressure drop in a cavity is measured for a constant flow rate flow the permeability can be easily measured applying the original formulation of Darcy's Law:

$$Q = - A (k/\mu) (\Delta P/L) \tag{16}$$

where A is the transversal area and L the length of the die. Normally more than one pressure measurement can be performed locating several transducers along the flow pattern in order to obtain information about the uniformity of the fiber bed permeability.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A two dimensional model of the filling stage of the Resin Transfer Model (RTM) has been developed and solved numerically. Model results expressed in terms of flow front position, pressure-flow rate relationships and total filling time as function of the operating pressure, for processes conducted at constant flow rate or constant pressure respectively, have been applied to analyze the effect of different parameters like mold geometry, fiber bed permeability and resin rheology. Moreover, model results were compared with results obtained with commercial injection molding packages properly modified to account for the effect of the porous media on the mold thickness and resin viscosity. Finally, several methods for the experimental determination of fiber bed permeabilities were presented. These results can be directly applied to design the processing conditions and the equipment requirements for the fabrication of composite laminates by RTM.

6. REFERENCES

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